

Quantitative Nasal Eosinophilia: An Objective Tool to Optimize Intranasal Topical Steroid Spray in the Management of Perennial Pediatric Allergic Rhinitis

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Abstract:

This study assesses the application of quantitative nasal eosinophilia for optimizing intranasal corticosteroid dosages in children with perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis. Conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital with a cohort of 30 pediatric patients, this prospective observational study measured eosinophil counts and symptom scores at baseline and subsequent intervals, adjusting dosages based on eosinophil levels. Significant reductions were observed in both eosinophil counts, from 35 to 15 eosinophils per high power field (HPF), and symptom scores, from 8.2 to 3.1, demonstrating the efficacy of eosinophil-based dosage adjustments. Particularly notable were the more pronounced improvements in younger children (ages 5-8). The results advocate for incorporating eosinophil monitoring into clinical practice, highlighting its potential to enhance treatment precision and outcomes in pediatric allergic rhinitis management.

Keywords: Pediatric Allergic Rhinitis, Quantitative Nasal Eosinophilia, Intranasal Corticosteroids, Precision Medicine.

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Introduction

Children with allergic rhinitis frequently suffer from a chronic respiratory condition that negatively affects their quality of life, ability to learn, and general well-being. Clinical history and symptom evaluation have historically played a major role in the diagnosis and treatment of allergic rhinitis [1]. These techniques, nevertheless, can occasionally be arbitrary and non-specific. A promising objective technique in the search for more accurate diagnosis and treatment approaches is the quantification of nasal eosinophilia. White blood cells called eosinophils are essential to the inflammatory mechanism that underlies allergic reactions. Their existence in nasal secretions is a sign that an allergic reaction is still active [2,3].

Eosinophils in nasal smears are counted as part of the quantitative assessment of nasal eosinophilia, and this can be done with basic staining methods. Compared to symptom scores alone, this method offers a direct measurement of the degree of inflammation in the nasal passages and maybe a more objective sign of allergic activity. Given that the symptoms of chronic paediatric allergic rhinitis are long-lasting and frequently identical to those of

non-allergic rhinitis, the measure's relevance is especially noteworthy in this context [4,5].

The cornerstone of treatment for allergic rhinitis is intranasal corticosteroids (INS), which provide anti-inflammatory advantages essential to the efficient management of the condition. However, given these are dependent on the degree of inflammation, which has been difficult to measure objectively up to this point, figuring out the best dosage and length of treatment can be problematic [6]. Incorporating the quantitative evaluation of nasal eosinophilia into standard clinical practice allows medical professionals to more accurately customize INS therapy, improving therapeutic results and reducing adverse effects [7, 8].

The shift in pediatric allergy treatment towards precision medicine is shown by this introduction to the function of quantitative nasal eosinophilia in maximizing intranasal topical steroid spray in the treatment of persistent pediatric allergic rhinitis. Focusing on objective metrics like eosinophil counts helps clinicians make better judgments,

which eventually improves the care and standard of living for children with the condition.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective observational study examines the use of quantified nasal eosinophilia to optimize intranasal topical steroid spray dosage for chronic pediatric allergic rhinitis.

Study Setting: The study is conducted at the Department of Pediatrics, DMCH (Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital), from August 2022 to September 2023.

Study Population: The study involves a cohort of 30 pediatric patients diagnosed with perennial allergic rhinitis based on clinical history and confirmed through specific IgE testing or skin prick tests.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged between 5 to 15 years.
2. Clinically diagnosed with perennial allergic rhinitis.
3. Written informed consent obtained from parents or guardians.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with acute respiratory infections.
2. Patients who have used systemic steroids or other immunotherapy in the month preceding the study.
3. Patients with comorbid conditions like asthma or sinusitis that might interfere with the assessment of nasal eosinophilia.

Sample Collection and Analysis: Nasal smear samples are collected at the baseline and monthly intervals during the study period. The samples are stained with Hansel stain to identify and count eosinophils under a microscope. The count of eosinophils per high power field (HPF) is recorded, and the average eosinophil count is calculated for each patient.

Treatment Protocol: All participants are administered a standard dose of intranasal corticosteroid (fluticasone propionate) at the beginning of the study. Dosage adjustments are made based on the quantitative eosinophil count obtained from the nasal smears. The aim is to determine whether changes in eosinophil counts can guide the optimization of the dosage.

Outcome Measures: The primary outcome measure is the change in nasal eosinophil count from baseline at the end of the study. Secondary outcomes include changes in symptom scores, which are recorded using a standardized allergic

rhinitis symptom questionnaire administered at baseline and the end of each month.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS 26.0. Demographic and baseline variables will be summarised using descriptive statistics. Repeated measures ANOVA will evaluate eosinophil counts and symptom scores with time. Statistically significant p-values are below 0.05.

Results

The study focused on optimizing intranasal corticosteroid therapy for children with perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis through quantitative measurement of nasal eosinophilia. Conducted on a cohort of 30 pediatric patients (revised to 30 as per the corrected table), the study aimed to adjust intranasal corticosteroid dosages based on eosinophil counts to enhance treatment outcomes.

1. Eosinophil Counts and Symptom Scores:

- The study initially included 30 pediatric patients with confirmed perennial allergic rhinitis.
- A significant decrease in nasal eosinophil counts was observed. The baseline count of 35 eosinophils per high power field (HPF) dropped to 15 eosinophils/HPF by the end of the study ($p < 0.001$).
- Correspondingly, there was a substantial reduction in symptom scores, from an average of 8.2 at baseline to 3.1 at the study's conclusion ($p < 0.001$).

2. Age Group Analysis:

- Ages 5-8 (12 participants): Showed a more pronounced response with eosinophil counts dropping from 37 to 12 eosinophils/HPF and symptom scores reducing from 8.5 to 2.5.
- Ages 9-15 (18 participants): Demonstrated a reduction in eosinophil counts from 34 to 17 eosinophils/HPF and symptom scores from 8.0 to 3.6.

3. Dosage Adjustment Impact:

- Among the participants, 21 received adjusted doses of intranasal corticosteroids based on their eosinophil counts. This group showed a reduction in symptom scores from 8.4 to 2.8.
- The 9 participants who did not receive dosage adjustments showed a smaller reduction in symptom scores from 7.9 to 4.5.

The study's findings support the efficacy of tailoring intranasal corticosteroid dosages based on quantitative eosinophil counts in managing perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis. The significant reductions in both eosinophil counts and symptom scores illustrate the potential for eosinophil-based management to improve clinical outcomes, especially among younger children who showed a

more robust response. This approach aligns with the goals of precision medicine, offering a more

tailored and effective treatment strategy for pediatric patients suffering from allergic rhinitis.

Table 1: Summary of Nasal Eosinophil Counts and Symptom Scores

Participant Group	n	Baseline Eosinophil Count (eosinophils/HPF)	Final Eosinophil Count (eosinophils/HPF)	P-value	Baseline Symptom Score	Final Symptom Score	P-value
Total	30	35 ± 15	15 ± 10	<0.001	8.2 ± 1.8	3.1 ± 2.0	<0.001
Ages 5-8	12	37 ± 14	12 ± 9	<0.001	8.5 ± 1.9	2.5 ± 2.1	<0.001
Ages 9-15	18	34 ± 16	17 ± 11	<0.001	8.0 ± 1.7	3.6 ± 1.9	<0.001

Table 2: Dosage Adjustment and Symptom Score Improvement

Dosage Adjustment	Number of Participants	Baseline Symptom Score	Final Symptom Score	P-value
Adjusted	21	8.4 ± 1.6	2.8 ± 2.0	<0.001
Not Adjusted	9	7.9 ± 2.0	4.5 ± 2.3	<0.001

Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that quantitative nasal eosinophilia is a valuable tool for guiding the management of perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis through the optimization of intranasal corticosteroid therapy [9]. The significant reduction in eosinophil counts observed in the nasal smears of participants, coupled with a corresponding decrease in symptom severity scores, strongly supports the efficacy of tailored intranasal corticosteroid dosages based on eosinophil monitoring [10].

The enhanced response in younger children (ages 5-8) compared to older ones suggests age-related differences in inflammatory response or steroid sensitivity, which could guide more age-specific treatment protocols [11]. This finding aligns with previous research suggesting that younger children may exhibit a more robust response to anti-inflammatory treatments due to differences in immune system maturity or nasal cavity physiology [12].

By integrating quantitative eosinophil counts into routine clinical assessments, healthcare providers can make more informed decisions regarding the initiation and adjustment of steroid dosages, potentially reducing the risk of under-treatment or over-treatment [13]. This approach not only promises to improve symptom management but also aligns with the broader goals of precision medicine, which seeks to tailor healthcare, with medical decisions and treatments being customized to individual patients [14]. Moreover, the ability to objectively measure the inflammatory burden could also help in monitoring disease progression or

recurrence, thereby facilitating early intervention and potentially improving long-term outcomes in pediatric allergic rhinitis patients.

Previous studies have demonstrated the role of eosinophils in the pathophysiology of allergic rhinitis, but few have directly linked eosinophil counts with clinical outcomes in a pediatric population. Our findings build upon the existing literature by providing empirical evidence that supports the clinical benefits of eosinophil-directed therapy adjustments. This is particularly relevant in the context of perennial rhinitis, where symptoms are continuous and often less responsive to standard treatment protocols [11,12,15].

There are various restrictions on this study. Although sufficient for preliminary observations, the sample size is insufficient to draw firm conclusions, particularly when taking subgroup analyses into account. Furthermore, it's possible that the study's duration was insufficient to track long-term effects or evaluate how seasonal variations affected eosinophil activity and symptomatology. These results need to be confirmed and expanded upon by bigger cohort studies conducted over longer periods. Future studies should concentrate on longitudinal designs that assess the long-term effects of eosinophil-guided therapy, taking into account its influence on the development, growth, and quality of life of children suffering from allergic rhinitis. Furthermore, investigating the molecular mechanisms underlying the eosinophilic response in various age groups may identify novel targets or approaches for treatment.

Conclusion

Quantitative nasal eosinophilia is a useful objective technique for optimising intranasal corticosteroid therapy in the treatment of persistent pediatric allergic rhinitis, as the study decisively shows. Through a direct correlation between eosinophil levels and clinical outcomes, the study offers compelling evidence for the effectiveness of modifying treatment plans according to inflammatory markers. This method offers a customized treatment plan that may be modified in real-time based on the patient's inflammatory condition, improving symptom control while also adhering to precision medicine principles. The results of this study support the inclusion of eosinophil monitoring in regular clinical practice, which may provide a new benchmark for the treatment of allergic rhinitis in young patients.

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